

Isoelectric PVC Mimicking AV Block!

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Description

The above electrocardiogram (ECG) was obtained due to pauses reported on telemetry. Figure A is lead II (simulating telemetry lead configuration) showing what seemed to be an uncondacted atrial beat (red arrow), which marched with the underlying sinus P waves, concerning for Mobitz II second degree atrioventricular (AV) block, versus an uncondacted premature atrial contraction (PAC), given the slightly different morphology compared to sinus P waves. Figure B, the 12-lead ECG, demonstrates that this complex was in fact an isoelectric premature ventricular contraction (PVC), as seen in other precordial leads (blue arrows). Figure C shows the limb lead pattern of the PVC (green arrows), yielding a -30° axis, causing it to be isoelectric in lead II, mimicking an uncondacted atrial activity on telemetry.

Discussion

Isoelectric PVCs were reported to result in pauses on telemetry without concurrent pacemaker firing, giving the impression of pacemaker dysfunction [1]. Multiple surface ECG leads and intracardiac electrograms identified the PVCs. Another case reported symptomatic ectopic beats detected by an Apple Watch, missed on Holter, found to be isoelectric PVCs requiring ablation for symptom relief [2].

Manuscript submitted June 14, accepted June 23, 2025
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<https://cardiofellows.com/newsletter-june-2025.html>

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KEYWORDS: Isoelectric PVC; Atrioventricular Block; Arrhythmia, Artifact.

Reference this article as:

Parks A, Nagaraj S, As Sayaideh M, Malik H, Ruiz B, Odigwe C, Omar B, Manoharan S, Malozzi C. Isoelectric PVC Mimicking AV Block! Cardiofel Newslet 2025. June; 8(6):12 – 13.